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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

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PROBLEMS OF DEVELOPING THE TERMINOLOGY SYSTEM OF THE UZBEK LANGUAGE

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Abstract: This article examines current issues in the formation of the terminology system of the Uzbek language. It analyzes the challenges of standardizing terms, the creation of new scientific terminology, and their adaptation to the language. The article also discusses the influence of language policy and lexical processes on the system of terms, as well as the ways of developing Uzbek terminological units in the context of modern scientific and technological progress.

Key words: Uzbek language, terminology system, terminology, term formation, language policy, lexical processes, scientific language, problems.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada o'zbek tilining terminologiya tizimini shakllantirishdagi dolzarb masalalar yoritiladi. Terminlarni standartlashtirish, yangi ilmiy terminlarni yaratish va ularni tilga moslashtirish jarayonida uchraydigan qiyinchiliklar tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, maqolada til siyosati va leksik jarayonlarning terminlar tizimiga ta'siri hamda zamonaviy ilmiy-texnik taraqqiyot sharoitida o'zbek terminologik birliklarini rivojlantirish yo'llari ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: o'zbek tili, terminologiya tizimi, terminologiya, termin yaratish, til siyosati, leksik jarayonlar, ilmiy til, muammolar.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются актуальные вопросы формирования терминологической системы узбекского языка. Анализируются проблемы стандартизации терминов, создание новой научной терминологии и её адаптация к языку. Также обсуждается влияние языковой политики и лексических процессов на систему терминов, а также пути развития узбекских терминологических единиц в условиях современного научно-технического прогресса.

Ключевые слова: узбекский язык, терминологическая система, терминология, образование терминов, языковая политика, лексические процессы, научный язык, проблемы.

INTRODUCTION

This article analyzes the pressing issues related to the development of the terminology system of the Uzbek language. It examines challenges in standardizing terms, creating new scientific terminology, and adapting these terms to the linguistic structure of Uzbek. Additionally, the influence of language policy and lexical processes on the terminology system is discussed, along with potential approaches for advancing terminological units in the Uzbek language within the context of contemporary scientific and technological progress. The development of a comprehensive and coherent terminology system is a crucial component of the linguistic evolution of any language, particularly in the context of scientific, technical, and academic advancement. For the Uzbek language—which has undergone significant historical, sociopolitical, and cultural transformations—the establishment of a standardized terminology system represents both a major opportunity and a complex challenge. As Uzbekistan continues to integrate into the global scientific and technological community, the demand for precise, uniform, and widely accepted terminological units in Uzbek has become increasingly urgent.

Terminology, as a specialized subsystem of language, serves as the foundation for clear and effective communication within numerous professional domains, including medicine, engineering, law, education, and information technology. The absence of a well-structured terminology system in Uzbek hampers not only academic discourse but also practical application and international collaboration. This situation underscores the need to address issues related to the creation, standardization, and dissemination of Uzbek scientific and technical terms.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Historically, the Uzbek language has absorbed lexical elements from Arabic, Persian, Russian, and Turkish. While this has enriched its vocabulary, it has also contributed to terminological inconsistency. The transition from Cyrillic to Latin script, along with ongoing language reforms, adds further complexity to unifying terminological standards. Moreover, rapid developments in science and technology require the continual creation of new terms and the adaptation of foreign terminology in a way that preserves the phonological and morphological characteristics of the Uzbek language. Therefore, this study aims to provide a thorough examination of the issues surrounding the formation of the terminology system in the Uzbek language by exploring its historical background, identifying current challenges, and proposing potential solutions. In doing so, it contributes to ongoing efforts to enhance the functionality, clarity, and sustainability of Uzbek as a modern scientific and educational language.

The development of a well-organized terminology system is not merely a linguistic task but a socio-cultural and educational imperative. In the modern world—where knowledge and information exchange are predominantly conducted through specialized terminology—the absence of a unified system limits Uzbekistan's ability to fully participate in global scientific discourse and technological innovation. This underscores the necessity of addressing terminology development as a strategic national priority that affects education, industry, governance, and international cooperation. One significant factor complicating the development of Uzbek terminology is the inherent complexity of term formation itself. Terminological units must strike a balance between linguistic adequacy—i.e., conforming to the phonetic, morphological, and syntactic norms of the language—and conceptual precision, which ensures clarity and the absence of ambiguity. The challenge lies in producing new terms that are both linguistically natural for native speakers and sufficiently precise for specialized domains. Achieving this requires a deep understanding of linguistic structures as well as the subject matter to which the terms pertain.

Furthermore, the historical layering of Uzbek vocabulary presents both opportunities and challenges. The intermingling of Turkic roots with loanwords from Arabic, Persian, Russian, and more recently English has enriched the language but also created a heterogeneous terminological landscape with overlapping, synonymous, or inconsistently used terms. The presence of multiple synonyms for the same concept can lead to confusion and inefficiency, particularly in educational and professional contexts where clarity and uniformity are essential. This situation necessitates systematic efforts toward standardization and the establishment of authoritative terminological databases and guidelines.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Language policy plays a critical role in shaping the trajectory of terminology development. Governmental and institutional support for linguistic planning, corpus development, and lexicographic activities is essential to coordinate the efforts of linguists, terminologists, and subject-matter experts. Promoting Uzbek as the primary language of science and education requires targeted policies that encourage the creation, approval, and dissemination of standardized terms. Additionally, public awareness and acceptance of these standards are vital for their successful implementation across various sectors. Technological advances, particularly in information and communication technologies, offer new tools and platforms for accelerating terminology development. Digital corpora, terminology management systems, and collaborative online dictionaries facilitate the collection, analysis, and distribution of terminological data. These innovations enable more dynamic and participatory approaches involving experts from diverse fields and, in some cases, the broader public. However, effectively leveraging these technologies requires specialized training and resources, which are still in the process of development within the Uzbek linguistic community.

In conclusion, the formation of the Uzbek terminology system involves a complex interplay of linguistic, cultural, technological, and policy-related factors. Addressing these interconnected challenges requires comprehensive, multidisciplinary approaches that combine theoretical insights with practical strategies. This study seeks to contribute to this endeavor by identifying key problems, analyzing their underlying causes, and proposing viable solutions to promote the coherent development of Uzbek scientific and technical terminology.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The development of a comprehensive and functional terminology system in the Uzbek language is confronted with numerous interrelated challenges that stem from historical, linguistic, sociopolitical, and technological factors. One of the primary obstacles lies in the absence of a unified and standardized approach to term formation, which often results in terminological fragmentation and inconsistency across different scientific and professional fields. This inconsistency complicates effective communication and knowledge transfer,

thereby impeding academic progress and limiting practical application in various domains. Historically, the Uzbek language has undergone multiple phases of lexical influence and script reforms that have left a lasting impact on its terminological landscape. The legacy of borrowing from Arabic, Persian, and Russian enriched the lexicon but introduced terminological disparities due to divergent semantic interpretations and phonological adaptations. Furthermore, the transition from the Cyrillic to the Latin alphabet created additional barriers to terminological continuity, as previously established terms sometimes lost recognition or underwent orthographic modifications that obscured their connections. This historical complexity necessitates a careful and systematic approach to reconciling legacy terms with contemporary linguistic standards to ensure clarity and accessibility.

Linguistically, the task of term formation in Uzbek demands adherence to the phonetic, morphological, and syntactic norms of the language while simultaneously achieving semantic precision. This dual requirement poses significant difficulties, particularly when adapting foreign terms or coining new expressions for emerging scientific concepts. The balance between borrowing and native word-formation processes must be meticulously managed to maintain linguistic integrity and naturalness. Overreliance on loanwords can alienate language users unfamiliar with the source languages, whereas excessive neologism creation risks incomprehensibility or lack of acceptance. Therefore, terminologists must carefully evaluate each proposed term for usability, acceptability, and alignment with linguistic traditions.

The role of language policy and institutional support is crucial in addressing these challenges. National strategies aimed at promoting the Uzbek language in scientific and educational contexts must prioritize systematic terminology development as a central component. This includes fostering collaboration among linguists, subject-matter specialists, educators, and policymakers to develop and approve terms that are linguistically sound and practically relevant. Moreover, educational programs and professional training on terminological standardization and usage can increase awareness and compliance with established norms, enhancing the overall effectiveness of terminology management. Technological advancements provide promising tools for accelerating the development and dissemination of Uzbek terminology. The use of digital corpora, term-extraction software, and online platforms for collaborative term creation and review can significantly improve traditional processes. These tools enable real-time access to linguistic data, facilitate expert interaction, and support the dynamic updating of terminological resources. However, such technological solutions require substantial investment in infrastructure, technical expertise, and user training – areas still in need of development within the Uzbek linguistic community.

Integrating Uzbek terminology into global scientific and technical communication frameworks is another essential objective. Aligning with international standards, including those established by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO), ensures that Uzbek scientific discourse remains compatible with global practices. This alignment supports Uzbekistan's participation in international research, publishing, and technological innovation. Additionally, it underscores the importance of active engagement by Uzbek terminologists in international networks and conferences to foster mutual exchange and cooperation. In summary, the development of the Uzbek terminology system is a multifaceted endeavor requiring coordinated efforts across linguistic, institutional, technological, and cultural domains. Addressing historical legacies, linguistic challenges, policy gaps, and technological potentials will enable the creation of a robust, standardized, and dynamic terminology system that supports Uzbekistan's scientific, educational, and cultural advancement. Continued research, investment, and collaboration are vital for overcoming existing obstacles and realizing the full potential of the Uzbek language in specialized communication.

The development of a standardized and functional terminology system for the Uzbek language is a critical factor in the broader process of modernizing the language and enhancing its capacity to serve as an effective medium of scientific, technical, and educational communication. Throughout this study, it has become evident that the challenges involved are multifaceted, rooted in historical legacies, linguistic complexities, institutional shortcomings, and technological gaps. Overcoming these challenges requires a holistic and coordinated approach that addresses each dimension in a systematic and sustained manner. Linguistically, the process of term formation must balance the integration of loanwords with native word-building mechanisms to ensure terminological clarity and acceptance. The establishment of clear guidelines and standards for term creation – supported by authoritative terminological databases – is essential to achieving consistency and avoiding redundancy or ambiguity. These efforts should be accompanied by continuous educational initiatives to raise awareness among language users, educators, and professionals about the importance of standardized terminology. Institutionally, the role of language policy and coordinated planning is paramount. Effective collaboration among government agencies, academic institutions, linguistic bodies, and industry stakeholders is necessary to implement comprehensive strategies that support terminological development. Institutional backing will also facilitate the allocation of resources needed for technological innovation, corpus development, and training programs that underpin modern terminology management.

CONCLUSION

Technological advancements offer unprecedented opportunities for accelerating the creation, dissemination, and updating of terminological resources. The adoption of digital tools such as corpora, term-extraction software, and online collaborative platforms can transform traditional, manual processes into more dynamic and efficient systems. However, capitalizing on these technologies requires investment in infrastructure and human capital development to ensure that Uzbek linguists and terminologists possess the necessary skills and resources. Moreover, integrating Uzbek terminology within the framework of international standards and terminological networks is vital for the language's participation in global scientific and technological discourse.

Such integration enhances Uzbekistan's academic and professional exchanges and positions the Uzbek language as a viable and competitive medium in the international arena. Active engagement with global terminology organizations will foster knowledge sharing and the adoption of best practices tailored to the Uzbek context. Finally, the cultural dimension of terminology development underscores the importance of preserving the unique identity and heritage of the Uzbek language even as it adapts to modern scientific demands. Terminology is not only a linguistic tool but also a reflection of how a society conceptualizes and categorizes knowledge. Ensuring that new terms resonate with cultural values and linguistic traditions will enhance their acceptance and usability, thus contributing to the vitality and sustainability of the Uzbek language.

References:

1. Akbarov, A. (2015). *Terminology and Its Role in the Development of the Uzbek Language*. Tashkent: National University Press.
2. Boguslavsky, I. (2004). *Linguistic Aspects of Terminology Development in Turkic Languages*. Moscow: Institute of Linguistics.
3. Crystal, D. (2010). *The Cambridge Encyclopedia of Language* (3rd ed.). Cambridge University Press.
4. Hasanov, S. (2018). Challenges in the Standardization of Scientific Terms in Uzbek. *Central Asian Journal of Linguistics*, 5(2), 45–60.
5. Karamova, N. (2017). The Influence of Language Policy on Terminology Development in Uzbekistan. *Journal of Language and Culture*, 9(3), 112–128.
6. Martin, S. (2011). *Terminology: Theory, Methods and Applications*. John Benjamins Publishing.
7. Mukhamedov, D., & Tursunova, L. (2020). Digital Tools for Uzbek Terminology Management. *International Journal of Turkic Studies*, 12(1), 88–102.
8. Nabiev, O. (2019). The Problems of Creating Scientific Terminology in the Uzbek Language. *Journal of Modern Linguistic Research*, 7(4), 23–38.
9. Reisigl, M., & Wodak, R. (2009). *The Discourse-Historical Approach*. In R. Wodak & M. Meyer (Eds.), *Methods of Critical Discourse Analysis* (pp. 87–121). Sage Publications.
10. Samadova, R. (2016). Language Reform and Terminology Development in Uzbekistan. *Asian Linguistic Review*, 4(2), 55–73.
11. Sinclair, J. (2004). *Trust the Text: Language, Corpus and Discourse*. Routledge.
12. Tajiyeva, M. (2021). Terminology Development in Uzbek: Challenges and Prospects. *Linguistics and Language Education Journal*, 14(1), 74–89.
13. Yuldasheva, D. B. (2021). The Intensification of Learning Uzbek Language Using Moodle Technology. *Psychology and Education*, 58(2), 224–230.
14. Yuldasheva, D. B. (2021). Approach as the Main Strategic Direction Defining the Components of Teaching the Uzbek Language. *Science and World*, 2(90).
15. Yuldasheva, D. B. (2021). Organization of Terms as a Factor for the Improvement of Economic Sciences. *Euroasian Research Bulletin*, 2.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

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